

DESIGN AND EMOTION INTO COLLECTIVE PUBLIC USE PRODUCTS?

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ABSTRACT

This study presents a pilot literature review, including articles published in international Design and Ergonomics journals from 2007 to 2013. Its main goal is to identify the presence of collective use products in the current scope of Design and Emotion. The classification and analysis of those articles is based on two approaches: (i) classification of the use of products regarding: collective product / individual and consumption product/ unspecified use product (ii) emotion types: positive emotions / negative / positive and negative / unspecified emotion. The results confirm the hypothesis about the significant lack of studies focusing on emotion and directed at collective public use products.

KEYWORDS: *Design and Emotion; products of collective-public use; literature review.*

INTRODUCTION

All material things evoke emotions—strong or subtle, positive or negative, conscious or unconscious—that directly affect the way people feel, think and behave (Damásio, 2000). Emotions are a necessary part of people's lives, because people don't react to the physical qualities of things, but rather what those things mean to them (Krippendorff, 2000). The feelings associated with the pleasurable use of products include safety, pride, excitement and satisfaction (Jordan, 2000), attraction, fascination and inspiration (Desmet, 2009) and people express affection for certain products to the point of "loving them" (Russian and Hekkert, 2007). Recent developments in the design discipline focus on the importance of designing for wellbeing and happiness (Desmet, 2012; Desmet and Pohlmeier, 2013; Dorrestijn and Verbeek, 2013).

In general, the authors refer to the emotion involved in using individual products, despite the fact that studies on collective use products may (and should) be enriched with answers that translate affective and therefore emotional reactions. The design of urban elements, for example, which are products of collective public use, does not differ from other design products (Creus, 1996): all kinds of products affect the emotions of their users, because there are no emotionally neutral products (Desmet and Hekkert, 2007). For example, frustrating interactions with products can reveal adverse effects, such as insecurity, fear and even anger (Norman, 2004).

Collective and public use products are aimed at meeting the, often indispensable needs (e.g. street furniture) needs of a larger number of users, compared to individual products or even private collective usage. Based on this principle, the aim of this study is to identify how the emotion associated with collective public use products is being addressed in the field of Design and Emotion. For this, the study presents a literature review including articles published in international journals from 2007 to 2013, which corresponds to about half of the life cycle of Design and Emotion. The product use approach was decisive for the motivation of this research study, based on the following questions: what kinds of products have a greater emphasis on works that are being carried out in the field of Design and Emotion? What are these products?

PRODUCTS OF USE

In areas such as management and marketing, for example, product distinction in specific categories usually has a central idea of classification, identifying public or consumer characteristics, in order to be certain of the strategies to use in market performance. In design, different industrial product categories correspond to distinct requests in the project that require one to keep in mind the following questions (Löbach, 2001, p. 41): (i) How is the product used? (ii) What is the meaning or value of the product for the user? (iii) How many different people use the product? And (iv) Is the product used collectively or privately?

The products have direct and indirect relations with users, and the intensity of these relationships (Figure 1) should be considered in the product developing process. The further a user is from owning or using a product, the greater his indifference to it (Löbach, 2001). For this reason, public-use products have a higher predisposition to predation, requiring a greater demand for maintenance that usually comes from the public coffers.

A systematic literature review was conducted in the following steps (MAGAREY, 2001): 1) problem definition, 2) search for articles, 3) selection and critical evaluation of articles, 4) data collection, 5) data analysis.

1. **Problem definition:** The definition of the problem, which constitutes the first step of the process, is the research into the relationship between collective public use products and the scope of the publications that have been conducted by the field of Design and Emotion, published in the design and ergonomics journals.
2. **Articles search:** The search period of publications comprises the last seven years (2007 to 2013), corresponding to the second half of the Design and Emotion study field. The selection of the analysis period is based on their representativeness (approximately 50 of the lifetime of the research area) and the major upgrade of articles. As a search strategy, a search for articles was undertaken using the keywords most used in the Design and Emotion literature: “design and emotion”, “emotional design”, “emotion in design” and “affective design”. The rationale for the selection of articles published in journals—rather than those published in Congress and Symposia publications in the form of books, theses and dissertations—is due to the careful evaluation that the texts are often subjected to before being accepted.
3. **Article selection and critical evaluation:** In the sequence, in the first stage, the evaluation was conducted using titles and subsequently summaries (abstract), re-

lating articles mapped with the guiding research objective. In certain situations, due to doubts about the summary, it was necessary to read certain articles in full, in order not to leave out important items for review. The articles chosen were those whose content matched the extraction criteria, and had variables associated with the relationship between emotions felt towards the products. A total of 91 articles were identified and 17 were rejected for not referring specifically to products (e.g. activities in the medical field, education, consumer shopping attitudes). Most of the articles emphasized on the relationship between emotion and brands.

4. **Data collection:** The 74 articles mapped resulting from the previous step, constitute the sample for this study and were organized in a spreadsheet, by year of publication.
5. **Data analysis:** Reading the articles gave rise to the preparation of approaches to data evaluation that were mapped and classified: (i) products categorized by use: consumption and individual use/ public or collective use/ unspecified use and others; and (ii) types of emotions covered: positive/ negative/ positive and negative/ unspecified emotions. In terms of the use approach, consumer products and individual use have been grouped and distinguished from products of collective and public use. The classification “unspecified and other” relates to studies that address products in general (not to mention the user group for which the products are intended), as well as the products that are not part of other product groups (e.g. handicrafts, private indoor environments).

RESULTS

The 74 works sampled were found in 13 international and national journals related to different areas of knowledge (Table 1).

Figure 1. Intensity of relations between user and product usage

	PRODUCTS		
EMOTIONS	CONSUMPTION AND INDIVIDUAL USE	COLLECTIVE	OTHER AND UNSPECIFIED
POSITIVE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Hassenzahl, M. et al. (2013). Int. Journal of Design - Couvreur, L. et al. (2013). Int. Journal of Design - Helander, M. (2013). Theoretical Issues in Ergonomics Science - Mariana S.; Linden, J. (2012). Work - Gkouskos, D.; Chenb, F. (2012), Work - Golightly, et al. (2012). Theoretical Issues in Ergonomics Science - Khalid, H. et al. (2012). Theoretical Issues in Ergonomics Science - Kamp, I. (2012). Applied Ergonomics - Postma; C. et al. (2012). Design Issues - Sonderegger, A.; Sauer, J. (2010). Applied Ergonomics - Lee, S. et al. (2009). Human Factors and Ergonomics in Manufacturing - Ludden, G.; Schifferstein, H. (2009). Int. Journal of Design - Lacey, E. (2009). Int. Journal of Design - Schifferstein, H. (2008). Int. Journal of Design - Ludden, G. et al. (2008). Design Issues - Barnes, C.; Lillford, S. (2007). CoDesign - Jordan, P.; Persson, S. (2007). CoDesign - Seva, R. et al. (2007). Applied Ergonomics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Desmet, P.; Pohlmeier, A. (2013). Int. Journal of Design - Dorrestijn, S.; Verbeek, P. (2013). Int. Journal of Design - Cho, E.; Kim, Y. (2012). Int. Journal of Design - Pizzato, G. et al. (2012). Work - Correia, W. et al. (2012). Work - Volkev, L. (2008). Design Studies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sääksjarvi, M.; Hellén, K. (2013). Int. Journal of Design - Petermans, A. et al. (2013). Int. Journal of Design - Bodker, M.; Browing, D. (2013). Int. Journal of Design - Mourthé, C.; Dejean, P. (2012) Work
NEGATIVE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fokkinga, S.; Desmet, P. (2013). Int. Journal of Design - Fokkinga, S.; Desmet, P. (2012). Design Issues - Tsao, Y.; Chan, S. (2011). Applied Ergonomics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pizzato, G. et al. (2012). Work 	
POSITIVE & NEGATIVE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Hwang, J. et al. (2013). Applied Ergonomics - Sonderegger, A.; Sauer, J. (2013). Applied Ergonomics - Carbon, C. et al. (2013). Int. Journal of Design - Huang, Y.; Chen, C.; Khool, L. (2012). Int. Journal of Industrial Ergonomics - Ozcan, E.; Egmond, R. (2012). Int. Journal of Design - Kujala, S.; Nurkka, P. (2012). Int. Journal of Design - Ozkaramanli, D.; Desmet, P. (2012). Int. Journal of Design - Helander, M. et al. (2012). Theoretical Issues in Ergonomics Science - Tonetto, L.; Costa, F. (2011). Strategic Design Research Journal - Fenko, A. et al. (2010). Applied Ergonomics - Wellings, T. et al. (2010). Applied Ergonomics - Karana, E.; Hekkert, P.; Kandachar, P. (2009). Material Design - Hekkert, P.; Desmet, P. (2009). Int. Journal of Design - Chitturi, R. (2009). Int. Journal of Design - Demir, E. et al. (2009). Int. Journal of Design - Jenkins, S. et al. (2009). Int. Journal of Design 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Broek, E. et al. (2009) Applied Ergonomics - Karlsson, M. (2007). CoDesign 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Stones, C. (2013). Int. Journal of Design - Reddy, S. et al. (2012). Work - van der Linden, J.; Brendlerb, C. (2012) Work - Ho, A.; Siu, K. (2012). The Design Journal - Szalma, J. (2009). Theoretical Issues in Ergonomics Science - Karana, E.; Hekkert, P.; Kandachar, P. (2008). Material & Design - Pennington, N. et al. (2007). CoDesign

	PRODUCTS		
EMOTIONS	CONSUMPTION AND INDIVIDUAL USE	COLLECTIVE	OTHER AND UNSPECIFIED
POSITIVE & NEGATIVE	-Sauer, J., Sonderegger, A. (2009). Applied Ergonomics -Seva, R.; Helander, M. (2009). Int. Journal of Industrial Ergonomics -Rompay, T. et al. (2009). Int. Journal of Design -Blijlevens, J. et al (2009). Int. Journal of Design -Spence, C.; Zampini, M. (2007) CoDesign -Porter, C.; Porter, J.; Chhibber, S. (2007). Meeting Diversity in Ergonomics -Desmet, P.; Hekkert, P. (2007). Int. Journal of Design		
UNSPECIFIED	- Kim, S.; Cho, K. (2013). Int. Journal of Design - Campenhout, L. et al. (2013). Int. Journal of Design - Lockton, D. et al. (2013). Int. Journal of Design - Blijlevens, J. et al. (2013). Int. Journal of Design - Forslund, K. et al. (2013). Int. Journal of Design -Na, Y. (2009). Human Factors and Ergonomics in Manufacturing -Chamorro-Koc, M. et al. (2008). Design Studies		- Wastiels, L. et al. (2013). Int. Journal of Design -Camposa, L. et al. (2012). Work -Karana, E.; Hekkert, P.; Kandachar, P. (2010). Materials and Design

Table 1. Publications with kinds of emotions and products

Classifications of articles according to the category of use

Among the total publications, 74 (68.9%) discuss individual /consumption products, mainly cars, cell phones and electronics (Table 2), 32 (43.3%) focusing on positive and negative emotions.

Unlike the individual /consumption products, collective products are the minority in the revised publications; 9 assignments (12.2%) approached collective public use products (Figure 2): 2 relating to web sites; 3, to street furniture, 1 pub-

lic installation and, the other 4, relating to environments, or public spaces (elevator, toll roads, waiting room and library). Among the urban furniture, a bus shelter and gym equipment (Pizzato et al. 2012a and 2012b); a speedometer (Dorrestijn and Verbeek, 2013); an example of persuasive technology for wellbeing (a behavior-influencing design for wellbeing); and a Jazz shower (Desmet and Pohlmeier, 2013): a public installation that plays jazz, where to really hear the music, the user has to stand directly underneath a showerhead-like speaker, which is designed to enhance the experience so that the user feels immersed in the music.

	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	Total	%
Publications	8	5	15	4	2	21	19	74	100
Positive	3	3	3	1		10	8	28	37,8
Negative					1	2	1	4	5,4
positive/ negative									
	5	1	11	2	1	8	4	32	43,3
Unspecified		1	1	1		1	6	10	13,5
consumption/individual	6	3	13	3	2	12	12	51	68,9
Collective	1	1	1			4	2	9	12,2
Others	1	1	1	1		5	5	14	18,9

Table 2. Emotions, products and publications focused on reviewed articles by year of publication

<p>WEB SITES</p>		
<p>SPEEDOMETER</p>		

Figure 2. Cited collective public products

As the systematic literature review indicates, there are few works about public-use products, aimed at serving collective care for such products. This lack could be explained by the great difficulty in identifying the needs of a variety of users and the development of a product where relations with users tend not to be as intense as those involved when a product is for exclusive use, as pointed out by Löbach (2001).

CONCLUSION

Since its emergence approximately fourteen years ago, the field of Design and Emotion has instigated research in several areas of knowledge, from different nationalities, relating the use of, or the experience with products to emotion. In order to assess the type of emotion related to different products under consideration, and primarily aiming at the treatment of products of collective public use, this article presents a review and an analysis of publications in international Design and Ergonomics journals in the 2007 to 2013 period.

In order to systematize the grouping of articles, they were classified according to usage: a group for products of individual or consumption use, another for collective use and others or unspecified. The emotion types were classified as follows: “positive” emotions, “negative”, “positive and negative”, and “unspecified” emotion. The mapping of the articles published reinforces the interdisciplinary field and confirms the promi-

nence of the Delft University of Science and Technology (forerunner of Design and Emotion), in publications in the field.

The research hypothesis that collective public use products do not usually take part in the search scope of Design and Emotion was confirmed. The result shows that the focus of the publications in Design and Ergonomics areas of knowledge is on the individual consumer products. In general, there is a clear inclination for a simultaneous approach of positive and negative emotions. In addition, the author shows little interest in the approach to negative emotions, which often interfere with the product user to the point of the user abolishing use and/ or developing a fear of using the product.

Hopefully, with the mapping and classification of the articles, this study can be considered a contribution to the development of Design and Emotion research, mainly by the suggestion of the defiant demand of work aimed at meeting the numerous human and collective needs that exist in our society, which in terms of sustainability, should contribute to a world of responsible consumption.

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